

Thiazole Derivatives with Heterocyclic Substituents. Part-IV Merocyanines Derived from 2-methyl-4-(2'-Thienyl) and 2-Methyl-4-(2'-Furyl) Thiazoles

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A number of dimethin and tetramethin merocyanines derived from 2-methyl-4-(2'-thienyl and furyl) thiazoles have been prepared with a view to study the effect of these new heterocyclic substituents on absorption of the dyes.

IN the present investigation a number of dimethin and tetramethin merocyanines derived from 2-methyl-4-(2'-thienyl or furyl) thiazoles have been prepared and the absorption maxima data of these dyes were determined.

The variable acidic nuclei were derived from various ketomethylene compounds e.g., 2-phenyl-oxazolone, 1-phenyl-3-methyl-pyrazolone, and *N*-phenylrhodanine.

The vinylenic shifts observed in going from dimethin merocyanines (I, $n = 1$) to tetramethin merocyanines (I, $n = 2$) have been found to be between 90 nm to 100 nm.

I
[A = Acidic nuclei
 $n = 1, 2$
R = α -thienyl or furyl]

By comparing the absorption maxima data of these merocyanines (I) with the corresponding merocyanines (II) derived from 2-methyl-4-phenyl thiazole it has been observed that merocyanines (I) absorb at a shorter wave length (Table 1).

II
[A and n as in I]

In case of merocyanines the stability of the dipolar structure depends on the resonance interaction

between $>N-$ and $>C=O$ group as indicated in structure-III.

When a phenyl group is placed at position-4 in the thiazole ring, there is resonance interaction of the phenyl group with $>C=O$ group and this occurs at the expense of the main electron drift from $>N-CH_3$ to $>C=O$ which contributes to the amidic resonance (II)¹⁻⁴. As the stability of the dipolar structure is comparatively reduced, hypsochromic shift is consequently observed.

TABLE I—ABSORPTION MAXIMA DATA OF DIMETHIN AND TETRAMETHIN MEROCYANINES DERIVED FROM VARIOUS 2-METHYL-4-SUBSTITUTED THIAZOLES

Sl. No.	Nature of 'R'	Nature of acidic nucleus 'A'	Value of 'n'	Absorption maxima in $m\mu$
1.	Phenyl	2-Phenyl-5-oxazolone	1	532
2.	-do-	-do-	2	622
3.	α -Thienyl	-do-	1	525
4.	-do-	-do-	2	618
5.	α -Furyl	-do-	1	522
6.	-do-	-do-	2	615
7.	Phenyl	1-Phenyl-3-methyl-pyrazolone	1	501
8.	-do-	-do-	2	590
9.	α -Thienyl	-do-	1	488
10.	-do-	-do-	2	585
11.	α -Furyl	-do-	1	485
12.	-do-	-do-	2	585
13.	Phenyl	<i>N</i> -Phenyl rhodanine	1	515
14.	-do-	-do-	2	610
15.	α -Thienyl	-do-	1	505
16.	-do-	-do-	2	603
17.	α -Furyl	-do-	1	500
18.	-do-	-do-	2	600

Now if α -thienyl or α -furyl group is attached to the para-position of the phenyl group, the resonance interaction of these groups with $>C=O$ will be increased considerably because of the greater electron donating ability of S and O atoms which further decreases the stability of the dipolar structure thereby resulting in a hypsochromic shift(I).

Like similar dyes derived from 4-arylthiazoles these dyes are expected to possess excellent photographic sensitising properties.

Experimental

2-Methyl-4-(2'-thienyl)-thiazole was prepared from 2-acetyl thiophene by bromination and subsequent reaction of the bromo-compound with thioacetamide in absolute ethanol. 2-Methyl-4-(2'-furyl)-thiazole was prepared similarly from 2-acetyl-furan. The thiazoles were quaternised by heating with methyl iodide in a sealed tube.⁵

4-[3-Methyl-4-(α -thienyl)thiazoline-2-ylidene]-buten-1-ylidene]-1-phenyl-3-methyl-pyrazolone : 4-(3-Acetanilido allylidene)-1-phenyl-3-methyl-pyrazolone⁶ (0.35 g) and 2-methyl-4-(α -thienyl) thiazole methiodide (0.35 g) were refluxed in absolute ethanol and triethylamine (2 drops) for 10 mins. The compound was isolated in usual manner and recrystallised from ethanol.

Other tetramethin merocyanines were prepared in similar manner using either acetanilido allylidene or methoxy allylidene derivatives of desired keto-methylene compounds. The analytical data, mps. etc. of tetramethin merocyanines are given in Table 2.

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TABLE 2—DIMETHIN AND TETRAMETHIN MEROCYANINES (STRUCTURE—I)

Nature of 'R'	Nature of acidic nucleus 'A'	Value of 'n'	M.P. °C	Yield %	λ_{max} m μ	Carbon %		Hydrogen %	
						Found	Calc.	Found	Calc
α -Thienyl	2-Phenyl-5-oxazolone	1	185(d)	25	525	61.81	62.29	3.73	3.82
-do-	-do-	2	>250	15	618	64.08	64.29	3.85	4.09
α -Furyl	-do-	1	208	20	522	64.93	65.14	3.92	4.00
-do-	-do-	2	>250	10	615	66.83	67.02	4.08	4.06
α -Thienyl	1-Phenyl-3-methyl pyrazolone	1	193	25	488	63.32	63.32	4.25	4.49
-do-	-do-	2	>250	20	585	64.94	65.18	4.52	4.69
α -Furyl	-do-	1	174	25	485	65.98	66.12	4.65	4.85
-do-	-do-	2	230(d)	20	585	67.76	67.86	4.85	4.87
α -Thienyl	N-Phenyl-rhodanine	1	196(d)	30	505	54.87	55.07	3.17	3.38
-do-	-do-	2	>250	25	603	57.10	57.27	3.43	3.65
α -Furyl	-do-	1	>250	25	500	56.93	57.29	3.23	3.52
-do-	-do-	2	209(d)	15	600	59.18	59.43	3.54	3.78

4-[3-Methyl-4-(α -thienyl) thiazoline-2-ylidene] ethylidene-1-phenyl-3-methyl-pyrazolone : 2-Methyl-4-(α -thienyl) thiazole methiodide (0.4 g) and 4-(acetanilido methylene)-1-phenyl-3-methyl pyrazolone⁶ (0.34 g) were refluxed in absolute ethanol and triethylamine (2-drops) for 10 mins. The excess solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The desired product separated on cooling and was finally recrystallised from ethanol.

Dimethin merocyanines of other keto-methylene compounds were prepared similarly. The analytical data, mps. etc. of all dimethin merocyanines are given in Table 2.

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